

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B175
Date: 16 Feb 2006
Take Off: 08:51:43
Landing: 14:15:38
Flight Time: 5h23m55s

Campaign: DODO
Trials Instructions: Biomass / Aerosol Sampling
Operating Area: North of Dakar

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
5	Flight Manager / Core Chem	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	VACC / WAS / AMS / Core Chem / Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
7	AVAPS / CCM2 / CCN / CVI	Paul James	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
9	Filters	Claire McConnell	Reading University
10	Wet Neph	James Bowles	Met Office
11	SWS / SHIMS	Ian Rule	Met Office
12	ARIES	Alan Vance	Met Office
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			

Flight Track:

B175 Track 16-FEB-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b175

Date: 16 Feb 2006

Project: DODO

Location: North of Dakar, predominantly inland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
083151		engine start	0.05 kft	007	
083228		inu to nav	0.05 kft	007	
083456		power change	0.05 kft	007	
083703		taxy start	0.05 kft	007	
083854		asp open	0.05 kft	286	
085143		T/O	0.04 kft	353	
085143	091856	Profile 1	1.2 - 23.0 kft	042	
091856	093611	Run 1	23.0 kft	027	
093611	100347	Profile 2	23.0 - 0.67 kft	028	
093807		nevz zero	21.3 kft	030	
100347	102801	Run 2	0.67 - 1.0 kft	030	qnh estimate 1018
102801	104347	Profile 3	1.0 - 15.0 kft	063	qnh estimate 1018
104553	111231	Run 3	15.0 kft	227	
105524		tapes change	15.0 kft	249	
105957		sonde 1	15.0 kft	249	launch
111340	111445	Orbit 1	15.0 - 14.7 kft	113	
111546	111650	Orbit 2	15.1 kft	011	
111809	112324	Run 4	15.0 kft	035	
112351	112520	Orbit 3	15.0 - 15.1 kft	083	
112604	112731	Orbit 4	15.0 kft	158	
112928	113928	Run 5	15.0 kft	237	
114138	115259	Profile 4	15.0 - 4.9 kft	002	
115442	120441	Run 6	4.9 kft	190	
120648	121516	Profile 5	4.9 - 0.73 kft	351	
121753	121909	Orbit 5	1.3 kft	280	
121946	122100	Orbit 6	1.3 kft	356	
122150	122328	Orbit 7	1.3 kft	055	
122428	122620	Orbit 8	1.3 kft	119	
122705	122807	Profile 6	1.3 - 0.78 kft	220	
122807	123809	Run 7.1	0.77 - 0.72 kft	217	
123936	124738	Run 7.2	0.77 - 0.83 kft	026	
124857	130604	Profile 7	0.79 - 22.0 kft	214	
141538		Land	0.07 kft	356	at Dakar
142112		standstill	0.08 kft	335	14'44.61N, 17'29.45W

B175 Track 16-FEB-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO Flight: Validation (or not) of CAMM dust storm; radiative effect of dust

Flight No: B174

Date: 16th February 2006

Objectives:

1. Validation of CAMM dust storm
2. Radiative effect and in-situ sampling of dust over coastline

Location: Over ocean North of Dakar, and across North Western parts of Mauritania.

NULET: 18 25N 17 13W BIKIS: 16 45N 17 20W A: 18 25N 15W

Weather: Cloud free essential for most of sortie. Dust loading essential for most of sortie.

Special requirements: Low-level flying over ocean, low level, 500ft flying over land. Drop-sondes.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar. Open air sample pipes on runway.
2. Profile ascent to FL230 on a heading towards ULNET.
3. Descend at INDINI towards ATAR to FL045
4. Perform a saw tooth profile between FL045 and MSA towards ARISA until dust encountered.

5. If dust found in Northern Mauritania, proceed towards coastline along line east-west between point A and NULET or wherever appropriate and [max 120 mins]
 - a) SLR west towards sea at 500ft (or MSA) and continue oversea for 10 minutes after crossing coastline.
 - b) Set of 4 orbits at 500ft at 50 degree bank angle approximately 35 miles off coast [10mins,T=10].
 - c) Turn onto reciprocal heading and repeat the SLR (radiometers point up) [20 mins,T=50]
 - d) Turn onto reciprocal heading and profile ascent to 2500ft at 500ft/min [5mins,T=55].
 - e) SLR at 2500ft for 15 mins, heading east (should cross coastline half way along the run) [15 mins, T=70].
 - f) Broken profile ascent to 6000ft at 1000ft/min, turning onto reciprocal heading [5 mins,T=75].
 - g) SLR at 6000ft for 15 mins, heading west (should cross coastline half way along the run [15, mins,T=90].
 - h) Turn onto reciprocal heading (east) and profile ascent at 1000ft/min to FL180, prepare dropsonde launch and drop once reached FL180 [15 mins,T=105].
 - i) Turn onto heading to be determined by mission scientist and profile descent to FL030 at 1000ft/min [15 mins,T=120].
6. If dust encountered over land further north, perform [60 mins]:
 - a) A 10 min SLR at MSA, SWS and ARIES down (10 mins)
 - b) A series of 4 orbits at maximum bank angle (10 mins)
 - c) A 10 min SLR on a reciprocal heading at MSA, SWS and ARIES up (10 mins)
 - d) Profile ascent to within the dust layer
 - e) 10min SLR within the dust layer (10 mins)
 - f) Profile ascent to above the dust layer
 - g) 10 min SLR above dust layer, SWS and ARIES down (10 mins)
 - h) 10 min SLR above dust layer on a reciprocal heading (10 mins)

If no dust found, ascend to high level and transit to Dakar as fast as possible.

7. Return Dakar.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B175

Date: 16th February 2006

Sortie Objectives: In-situ sampling of Saharan dust over the land. Validation (or not) of CAMM large dust storm. Radiative effect of dust over land.

Operating area: Land areas north of Dakar and in northern Mauritania towards Western Sahara.

Weather: Mostly clear skies.

Flight Patterns:

Following take off from Dakar, a profile ascent over the ocean to the north revealed small scattering particles in the lowest 1000ft followed by a peak of larger particles at 2500ft. Clean air above FL050. High level transit to point Idini where a descent to FL500ft was performed. It was increasingly dusty below whilst moving north. Dust layer below FL095, with most dust below 3000ft. Some scattered Ci on horizon and more extensive to the east. PCASP showed a broad spectrum of particle sizes. Scattering approached $200 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$. Optical depth around 0.3. A SLR at 500ft was performed heading north towards the Western Sahara border. Surface below alternated between sand dunes and rock striations. Some larger rocky outcrops. Scattered camels and Bedouin camps. Since the concentrations were still below that expected from the CAMM model output, and the model predicted an elevated layer, a profile was performed to FL150. Suggestion of larger particles at elevated level around FL050. Considerable Cu to west and north of region.

Given maximum range of the aircraft, a turn was made onto a reciprocal heading, and an SLR performed at FL150 to bring above typical sand surface rather than rocky region. A sonde was dropped. A set of 2 60 degree orbits were performed. These were too far away from the sun, so a further set of 2 orbits at 45 degrees bank were performed above sand dunes. A further SLR at FL150 was performed on a reciprocal heading with radiometers pointing down.

At the end of the run, we descended to FL050, turned and performed one SLR at this altitude. At the end of the run, we turned and descended along a reciprocal heading to 500ft. A set of 2 orbits at SZA+10 degrees, and a set of 2 orbits at SZA were performed at around 1000ft under the previous high level orbits. Two reciprocal SLRs at 500ft were performed, one with SWS and ARIES up to examine the radiative effect, and one down to characterise the surface. A final profile ascent towards Indini was performed showing a deep dust layer to 5000ft, a sharp fall off with a shoulder at 8500ft and falling off completely above FL100. Transit performed at FL220 back to Dakar.

Summary:

An excellent radiation flight. Although dust loading in North of Mauritania was moderate, clear skies meant radiation work and orbits were completed. Some good in-situ sampling work. Dust forecast loads too heavy, and extent of outflow too large.

Problems

ARIES operator ill during flight.

Ellie Highwood

SWS, ARIES, Filters,
 SLR for core chem
 5000ft check Hugh
 VACC
 if that was dust-head

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.175**
 FAAM © 2004

Date **16./2./06**

Page **1** of **5**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0830					Dakar, T=17°C 1/2 Ci Early mist but not hazy otherwise Td=17 Wind northerly
~ 0850					T/O Haze over sea and to east.
085143	P1↑				Some Ci over sea to south. 500gr/min Sea state 1 much calmer than previous days 1000gr/min..
		4000gr			Scattered cirrus around, more extensive to easterly horizon Into clear sky here.
					5 elevated light dust 4 sea ~ 80 m ⁻¹ 2 1/2 ft. 2 1/2 dust O ₃ reduced? sea salt? small particles 50 100 150
		FL170			BBRs suggest relatively clear. Clear slot
	pend R1	F2230			Minor 4 in sea, small particles ~ FL100 but with elevated CO = O ₃
					Visibility good below, cloud to east, multiple layers.

Switch in headset lead
 Laptop stowage forward.

Accessible cupholder / tumbler hole!

dropside 8
 1 orbitals 8
 2 orbits 16
 10

24
 16
 40
 50

high

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.175**

Date **16/2/06**

Page **2** of **5**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09 48 ³⁶ 11	R1 P2	FL230↓			Dust below? Light if at all.
094814					Increasingly dusty below?
		FL100 40			Dust at below FL095
					sea only 50 m ⁻¹ but
					definitely dust. here. Higher
					than over land.
					Medium sized particles
					2D 100, SID 15? (or 50)
					500 gr/min below 3000g
					Broad spectrum
100342	R2 R2	500ft 3000ft			Sea 200 m ⁻¹ below
					falls away below ≈ 0.3
					Sand dunes, alternating with
					glatter marks areas
1014 31					Sea up to 250 m ⁻¹
102759	R2 P3↑	1000ft↑			Start profile up to avoid
					terrain and capture scattering
103247	P3↑	3000ft↑			1000gr/min
					Large particles at elevation
					Cu at top of high terrain
					Cloud
104347	P3end	FL150			Considerable Cu to west and
					North.
					Turn onto reciprocal.
					SLR for 15 mins at altitude

15 mins
 dropsonde FL150
 + 8 mins SLR 150
 2 orbits

Σ

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B...175**
 FAAM © 2004

Date16/2/06.....

Page **2** of5

GMT	Run/ Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104553	R3	FL150			NW westerly winds?
105959		FL150			Dropsonde
111231	R3end	FL150			
111340	01	FL150	90		Start orbit } 60° too far away from sun -oops
111445	01	FL150		End orbit	
	02	FL150		Start orbit	
111540	02	FL150	030		Start orbit
111649	02				
112324	R4	FL150			
112351	R4end 03	FL150	090		Start orbit 45° bank.
112520	03	FL150			End orbit
112604	04	FL150			Start orbit Sand dunes
112731	04	FL150			End orbit below
112928	R5	FL150			Running away from rocky outcrop.
					Some Ci on horizon
113928	R5				End run
114138	P4	FL150 ↓ 9000ft			Descend to FLO50
115259	P4	FLO50			End of profile
115442	R6	FLO50			Start run FLO50, in dust Sea ~ 125 m ⁻¹
120441	R6				end run. Dunes below.
120648	P5	FLO50 ↓			Descend to MSA 1000gr/min 500gr/min SZA = 35°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...175**.....

 Date **16/2/06**.....

 Page **4** of **5**

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run/ Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121516	P5	500ft			End profile Sca 200m ⁻¹
121753	05	1000ft	290		Start orbit } End orbit } 45°
121908	05	-1-			
121946	06	-1-			Start orbit } end orbit }
122100	06	-1-			
122150	07	-1-			Start orbit } End orbit } 35°
122328	07	-1-			
122428	08	-1-	130		Start orbit } End orbit }
12262	09	-1-	130		
	P6				Descend to MSA
122907	P6				
122907	R7.1	500ft			Sca 180 m ⁻¹ SWS/ARIES ↑ Dunes below "Soft ride"
123809	R7.1				End run
123936	R7.2				Start reciprocal run Sca ~ 250 m ⁻¹ Scattered cumulus below!! 2DC images suggest < 200µm so relatively small.
124738	R7.2				End Scattering ↑ 50m ⁻¹ in 2 hours → suggests storm coming? or to west? (or just more SW)
124857	P7	500ft			1000ft/min, orbit BL ~ 6000ft?? Turbulence

Here

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 16/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
----------------	---------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
08:51:43				Fail												Start Profile 1 from take-off	
08:54:20	200	0.11	Off	20	Noise											FL020	
09:56:37	220	0.10	Off	10	Noise											FL030	
08:57:57	175	0.09	Off	10	Noise											FL040	
08:58:59	16	0.10	Off		1											FL050	
08:59:58	10	0.12	Off		3											FL060	
09:01:12	15	0.12	Off		1											FL070	
09:02:17	15	0.11	Off													FL080	
09:03:23	15	0.10	Off													FL090	
09:04:20	60	0.11	Off													FL100	
09:05:29	26	0.11	Off													FL110	
09:06:23	10	0.10	Off													FL120	
09:07:34	15	0.11	Off													FL130	
09:08:40	13	0.12	Off													FL140	
09:09:45	5	0.12	Off													FL150	
09:10:56	8	0.13	Off													FL160	
09:12:11	5	0.12	Off													FL170	
09:13:12	10	0.11	0													FL180	
09:14:13	9	0.10														FL190	
09:15:30	10	0.10														FL200	
09:16:36	10	0.13														FL210	
09:17:40	6	0.10														FL220	
09:18:55																End of Profile 1 & Start Run 1 @ FL230	
09:19:00	7	0.13															
09:21:00	7	0.11															
09:23:00	10	0.11															
09:25:00	15	0.11															
09:27:00	10	0.11															
09:29:00	12	0.12															
09:31:00	10	0.12															
09:33:00	10	0.10															
09:35:00	10	0.09															
09:36:11	7	0.09														End of Run 1 & Start Profile 2 from FL230	
09:37:20	10	0.09														FL220	
09:38:22	25	0.09														FL210	
09:39:22	16	0.09														FL200	
09:40:22	15	0.09														FL190	
09:41:33	20	0.10														FL180	
09:42:52	18	0.08														FL170	
09:43:50	8	0.08														FL160	
09:45:03	15	0.08														FL150	
09:46:05	20	0.08														FL140	
09:47:09	20	0.08			Noise											FL130	
09:48:15	15	0.07			Noise											FL120	
09:49:35	20	0.08			Noise											FL110	
09:50:45	15	0.10			Noise											FL100	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 16/02/06 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 07:35:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 2 of 4**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:51:57	50	0.10		5	Noise											FL090	
08:52:59	100	0.11		15	Noise											FL080	
08:54:05	100	0.10		20	Noise											FL070	
08:55:10	140	0.11		20	Noise											FL060	
08:56:18	100	0.12		20	Noise											FL050	
08:57:25	140	0.12		40	Noise											FL040	
08:59:00	230	0.14		100	Noise											FL030	
10:01:00	204	0.13		100	Noise											FL020	
10:03:12	250	0.12		80	Noise											FL010	
10:03:47																End of Profile 2 & Start Run 2 @ 500'	
10:04:00	220	0.13		80	Noise												
10:06:00	240	0.13		80	Noise												
10:08:00	220	0.12		80	Noise												
10:10:00	250	0.12		90	Noise												
10:12:00	280	0.12		90	Noise												
10:14:00	270	0.12		90	Noise												
10:16:00	300	0.12	Off	90	Off												
10:18:00	300	0.12	Off	90	Off												
10:20:00	290	0.12	Off	80	Off												
10:22:00	290	0.12	Off	80	Off												
10:24:00	305	0.12	Off	80	Off												
10:26:00	300	0.11	Off	80	Off												
10:28:02																End of Run 2 & Start Profile 3 from 500'	
10:29:33	240	0.12	Off	80	Off											FL020	
10:31:36	170	0.13	Off	70	Off											FL030	
10:33:12	150	0.13	Off	70	Off											FL040	
10:34:08	130	0.13	Off	70	Off											FL050	
10:35:10	130	0.12	Off	60	Off											FL060	
10:36:02	100	0.12	Off	30	Off											FL070	
10:36:58	100	0.11	Off	20	Off											FL080	
10:37:57	70	0.11	Off	10	Off											FL090	
10:38:51	60	0.11	Off	10	Off											FL100	
10:39:48	50	0.12	Off	10	Off											FL110	
10:40:46	30	0.10	Off	5	Off											FL120	
10:41:49	10	0.10	Off	2	Off											FL130	
10:43:45																End of Profile 3 @ FL150	
10:45:53																Start Run 3 @ FL150	
10:46:00	10	0.11	Off	1	Off												
10:48:00	10	0.09	Off	1	Off												
																Word crashed, loss of logs	
11:12:32																End of Run 3	
11:13:40																Start Orbits	
11:17:01																End Of Orbits	
11:18:15																Start Run 4 @ FL150	
11:19:00	18	0.11	Off		Off												
11:23:25																End of Run 4	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B175

Date: 16/02/06	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 07:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
----------------	---------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	---------------	-------------

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:23:56																Start Orbits @ FL 150	
11:27:31																End of Orbits	
11:29:29																Start Run 5 @ FL150	
11:30:00	Noise		Off		Off												
11:32:00	Noise		Off		Off												
11:34:00	Noise		Off		Off												
11:36:00	Noise		Off		Off												
11:38:00	Noise		Off		Off												
11:39:29																End of Run 5	
11:41:46	20	0.12	Off		Off											Start Profile 4 from FL150	
11:42:52	7	0.12	Off		Off											FL140	
11:43:58	10	0.10	Off		Off											FL130	
11:44:55	20	0.09	Off		Off											FL120	
11:45:58	20	0.10	Off		Off											FL110	
11:47:00	18	0.09	Off	1	Off											FL100	
11:48:08	100	0.09	Off	15	Off											FL090	
11:49:17	120	0.10	Off	30	Off											FL080	
11:50:32	140	0.11	Off	30	Off											FL070	
11:51:31	125	0.11	Off	20	Off											FL060	
11:52:57	175	0.12	Off	60	Off											End of Profile 4 @ FL050	
11:54:42																Start Run 6 @ FL050	
11:55:00	150	0.12	Off	70	Off												
11:57:00	135	0.12	Off	70	Off												
11:59:00	140	0.12	Off	60	Off												
12:01:00	145	0.13	Off	80	Off												
12:03:00	130	0.13	Off	60	Off												
12:04:42																End of Run 6	
12:06:51																Start Profile 5 from FL050	
12:07:41	210	0.14	Off	100	Off											FL040	
12:09:09	210	0.13	Off	100	Off											FL030	
12:11:56	240	0.15	Off	90	Off											FL020	
12:15:12	260	0.14	Off	90	Off											End of Profile 5 @ 500'	
12:17:53																Start Orbits @ 1000'	
12:26:20																End of Orbits	
12:27:10																Start Profile 6 from 1000'	
12:28:09																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 7.1 @ 500'	
12:29:00	230	0.13	Off	90	Off												
12:31:00	220	0.13	Off	90	Off												
12:33:00	220	0.13	Off	80	Off												
12:35:00	250	0.14	Off	80	Off												
12:37:00	245	0.14	Off	90	Off												
12:38:10																End of Run 7.1	
12:39:37																Start Run 7.2 @ 500'	
12:40:00	240	0.13	Off	90	Off												
12:42:00	240	0.14	Off	90	Off												
12:44:00	230	0.14	Off	90	Off												

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B175

Date: DD/MM/YY

C) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	X	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	X	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	X X	
4) Log on to FLOODS	X	Condor
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	X	
6) In PVWAVE	X	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written 35213 blocks written Zero bad blocks
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	X	
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat	X	
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
iii) exit	X	
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	X	Don't worry about lots of FORTRAN run-time errors as long as the program continues. These are format errors when writing to ascii files.
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	X	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	X	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] Bnnn_seadas.dat	X	
d) Comment string:	X	
e) Start time: 0 if unknown	X	
f) End time: 240000 if unknown	X	
g) Read 2DC: Y	X	
h) Read 2DP: Y	X	
i) Secondary data: Y	X	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	X	
k) cmd.str: Y	X	
l) Auto time correction: N	X	
m) Full length secondary: N	X	
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)
Quick look at image blocks if required		
In PVWAVE		
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'		
i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY		
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:		
b) Flight number: Bnnn		
c) IWC plot: N		
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP		
e) Start time: 0 if unknown		
f) End time: 240000 if unknown		
g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10	Creates files	PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
iv) exit PVWAVE		
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log. 085200 z start time Note the particle type: 8 Last image at ~ 123735 z
b) Directory: PMSDATA:	X	
c) File generation: Hit enter	X	
d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data	X	
e) TAS: Y	X	
f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX	X	
g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty	X	
h) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	
i) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	X	
k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	X	
l) Coefficient choice: 2	X	
m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	X	
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 9h) and 9j).
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'	X	
iii) exit	X	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D	X	MFDC
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?	?	Some cloud after T/O, but no 2d-c images; images of dust later though

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B175

Date:

D) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing	X	
Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	X X	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW	X	Note the min size channel
a) Flight number: Bnnn	X	Note the volume flow rate
b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT	X	
c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP	X	
Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary)	X	
PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii)	X	
d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1	X	Bin 1 chosen
If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here	X X	1.6 ml/sec
e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value.	X	
Calibration files to be stored in ?????	X	
Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec	X	
f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d)	X	
g) Start time: Take-off or 0 if unknown	X	Look for realistic times in Flight Summary file or Cloud Phys operator log.
h) End time: Landing or 240000 if unknown	X	
3) In PVWAVE	X	Note: This will run quicker if you specify correct start / end times at 2g) and 2h).
i) enter:	X	
!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'	X	
Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!	X	
ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat'	X	
'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp'	X	
iii) exit	X	
4) MODIFY	X	
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp	X	
b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfd	X	
c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	X	MFDD
d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	X	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: Bnnn

Date: DD/MM/YY

E) NetCDF file preparation and ftp to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Run TAREXEC:MFD_BADC		
For inputs below, just press ENTER to use defaults		Defaults in [square brackets]
a) MFD to convert: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX b) version number for BADC: r[0] c) Names file: TARDIS_ROOT:[CALTEXT.NETCDF]CP_NAMES.TXT d) Directory: [DATA_ROOT:[NETCDF]] e) File prefix: [core-cloud-phy_faam] f) File suffix: [] g) File for output: [core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc]		As from 4c) above default NOT the default default default default Default name is generated
2) Ftp transfer to BADC		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - stage 1) creates two files: - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.nc - core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn.txt The *.txt file should be renamed to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_rm_Bnnn_descrip.txt but this cannot be done on VMS as the filename is too long You should do it if the file is first transferred to a PC, or after it has been uploaded to the appropriate "incoming" directory at BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd /incoming/faam/campaign-processed-core d) copy *.txt file as ascii e) copy *.nc and *2D-IMAGES.pdf files as binary		

F) BACKUP PROCEDURES		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Backup the intermediate files created in PMSDATA:		
a) zip "-V" PMSDATA:Bnnn*. * outdir:Bnnn_PMSDATA.zip Note that the uppercase "-V" option is important to preserve the VMS file characteristics when files are restored from this zip file.		Note destination directory "outdir"

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** Bnnn**Date:** DD/MM/YY

A) Raw data transfer to BADC		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer raw data files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt Bnnn_FFSSP.raw Bnnn_FFSSP_House_1.hse etc.		
2) Zip these file on the PC -output file: core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip		
3) Transfer SEADAS Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
4) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip) - rename Bnnn.zip to core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		
5) ftp to BADC a) ftp ftp.badc.rl.ac.uk b) login with username and password c) cd incoming/faam/campaign_raw d) bin e) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawffssp.zip f) put core-cloud-phy_faam_yyyymmdd_r0_bnnn_rawseadas.zip		Binary data transfer

B 174 15

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT ON	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	1	2	3	4	5	REMARKS
			22.45	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
1046			20.81	0.17	0.32	0.50			S
				404	369				D
				349	326	294			B
				2409	2377	2372			R
				1010.4	1010.3	1010.3			P
					3.00				
			21.73	0.17	0.32	0.50	0.73	1.08	S
			20.86	449	736	733	1135	1500	D
1234			20.33	342	334	325	331	462	B
			19.28	2382	2378	2378	2380	2382	R
			18.23	1011.2	1011.1	1011.2	1011.2	1011.4	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.06	0.17	0.31	0.51	0.73	1.11	S
1244			20.72	574	731	872	1078	1800	D
			19.94	250	253	254	281	281	B
			19.36	2396	2396	2399	2403	2401	R
			18.22	1011	1011	1011	1011	1011	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.05	0.18	0.32	0.51	0.74	1.08	S
1302			20.81	498	618	794	1237	1989	D
			20.07	228	227	237	237	263	B
			19.26	2423	2419	2416	2415	2409	R
			18.24	1011.7	1012	1012	1012	1012	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.07	0.18	0.31	0.47	0.73	1.12	S
1315			20.93	581	695	834	1364	1843	D
			20.15	224	240	248	248	414	B
			19.37	2401	2400	2400	2400	2400	R
			18.34	1012.7	1012.7	1012.7	1012.7	1012.7	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.57	0.17	0.32	0.51	0.73	1.1	S
1325			20.88	563	609	700	950	1207	D
			20.12	228	235	234	234	254	B
			19.41	2400	2400	2400	2400	2400	R
			18.29	1012	1012	1012	1012	1012	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.54	0.18	0.32	0.51	0.74	1.12	S
			21.03	492	603	959	1128	1803	D
1331			20.09	218	226	239	263	263	B
			19.54	2400	2400	2400	2400	2400	R
			18.34	1011	1011	1011	1011	1011	P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

T1 - T1
 T2 - T1
 T3 - T3
 T4 - T3
 +4 Tau
 on
 T3

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B175

Date:

16 FEB 2006

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 μ m Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
Except for				

Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B175Q9	----	----	Top	10:04:36	10:28:01	R2	3434	0.67–1.0 kft, possibly dust.
Filters run1	B175N7	----	----	Bottom	10:04:36	10:28:01	R2	2358	0.67–1.0 kft, possibly dust. Foil protection for stack crumbled slightly onto filter
Filters run2_a	B175Q11	----	----	Top	11:54:42	12:04:41	R6	1284	FL050, dust. Scattering coefficient 125 Mm-1
Filters run2_a	B175N8	----	----	Bottom	11:54:42	12:04:41	R6	799	FL050, dust. Scattering coefficient 125 Mm-1
Filters run2_b	B175Q11	----	----	Top	12:28:20	12:38:09	R7.1	1435	0.77–0.72 kft, dust. Scattering coefficient 180 Mm-1
Filters run2_b	B175N8	----	----	Bottom	12:28:20	12:38:09	R7.1	990	0.77–0.72 kft, dust. Scattering coefficient 180 Mm-1
Filters run2_c	B175Q11	----	----	Top	12:39:36	12:47:38	R7.2	1193	0.77–0.83 kft, dust. Reciprocal, scattering coefficient 250 Mm-1
Filters run2_c	B175N8	----	----	Bottom	12:39:36	12:47:38	R7.2	735	0.77–0.83 kft, dust. Reciprocal, scattering coefficient 250 Mm-1

2 then N

ARIES flight log

Flight: B175

Location: Mauritania

page 2 of 3

Date: 16-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
101653	R2	B175T	C	71	32	23	-190	25	CH1X1	
101756	"	U	C/O						Z1X5	
102234	"	V	C	71	32	24	-190	25	CH1X1	
102422	"	W	O	71	32	26	-190	26	Z1X5	(TAT15) EoR 102801 (SP3)
104627	R3	B175X	C	77.1	31	2.4	-190	24	CH1X1	Had HBB @ 80.
104733	"	Y	C/O	73.1	31	2.1	-190	24	Z1X3	
105033	"	B175Z	O	79.1	31	4.0	-190	20	CH1X1	
105223	"	B175Ø	O	70	31	4.4	-190	21	Z1X5	
105645	"	B1751	O/C						CH1X1	
105748	"	2	C	70	30	1	-190	20	CH1X1	
105822	"	B1753	C/O	70	30	1	-190	20	Z1X3	
1102	"	4							CH1X1	
110310	"	B1755	O	71	31	0	-190	17	Z1X4	
110655	"	B1756	C	71	31	-0.4	-190	15	CH1X1	
110804	"	B1757	O	70	31	-0.2	-190	16	Z1X4	
111147	"	B1758	C	70	31	-0.6	-190	17	CH1X1	
111344	O122	B1759	O/O						Z1X4	
111821	R	C175a	C	71	31	1.1	-190	17	CH1X1	
		b								aborted

WAKE UP!!! FOOL!!

ARIES flight log

Flight: B175

Location: MAURITANIA

page 3 of 3

Date: 16-2-6

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
112222		C175C	C	71	31	-0.8	-190	16	CH1x1	
112351	O 384	D	O						Z1x5	
1128 ~	R 5	C175E	e	71	31	-1.3	-190	15	CH1x1	
1130 ~	~	C175F	C						N1x5	
113424	"	G	C	71	31	-0.5	-190	19	CH1x1	
1136	"	H	C						N1x4	file handle fall over @ 1137 Back up
113856		C175I C175J	C	68.5	28.3	0	-190	20	CH1x1	
115415	R 6 ^{Flase} 5600	C175K	C	49↑	21↑	!			CH1x1	
115623	"	C175L	C	71	31	6.4	-190	21	CH1x1	
125724	"	C175M	O	71	31	9.1	-190	21	Z1x4	
120135 ?	~	C175O	e	71	31	13.7	-190	20	CH1x1	
120307	~	P	%						Z1x4	EoR @ 120441 ^{ARIES} Running on.
121535	O 586 LWB	Q R	C						CH1x1 Z1x5	
										Shall continues - log stops due to ill-health but the data should be ok - sorry.

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B175	Date	16/02/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	3
----------	------	------	----------	-----------------	----------	----------	---	----	---

Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0755						Laptop time set to DRS, SWS and SHIMS checked ok. SHIMS operated from laptop			
Note: Video working on the flight, a squirt of air duster might have done the trick									
085145	P1					T/o Dakar			
0859						Instruments now working			
090100						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 18			
0901	P1		Zen+6 fwd	100	500		X		
0901	P1			200	500			X	
091856	R1	FL230				End profile start run			
092200						Start video, count = 0:00:10.02			
092700						Shutters closed for 15s			
092807				75	250	SHIMS integ time changed, recording restarted, box temp = 20		X	
093000						Shutters closed for 15s, clear above			
093612	P2	FL230				End run, start profile			
094000						Shutters closed for 15s, box temp = 19/18			
0949						SHIMS nir dropped out, temp = 18??		X	
095039						SHIMS back up		X	
095200						Shutters closed for 15s, shims nir dropped out again			
095315						SHIMS back up			
095415						Shutters closed for 15s, skies clear and in dust...			
100348	R2	500'agl	Zen+6 fwd	100	500	End profile, start run	X		
1003				75	250			X	
102801	P3	500'agl				End run, start profile shutters closed			
102900	P3					Shutters open, box temp = 19			
1040						SHIMS nir dropped out			
104156						SHIMS back up			
104348		FL150				End profile, some cloud above, close shutters			
104554	R3	FL150	Zen+6 fwd	100	500	Start run, above dust, significant cloud below and level at start run, mostly clear above	X		
1102	R3	FL150	Zen+6 fwd	100	500		X		
1102	R3	FL150		75	250			X	
110500						Shutters closed for 15s			
111032				50	250	Shims integ time changed			
111232						End run			
111342	O1	FL150	Zen+6 fwd	100	500	Start orbit, LHD, shims nir dropped out, 60deg	X		
111446						End orbit	X		
111546	O2	"	"	75	250	Start orbit, shims nir dropped out, 60 deg	X		
111650						End orbit			
				75	250			X	
112353	O3		Zen+6fwd	50	250	Start orbit, shims nir dropped out, 60 deg	X		
112520						End orbit			

WAS Filling Log			
Operator - Hugh Coe			
Date	Bottle#	Start	End
16/02/2006	11	TBA	TBA
16/02/2006	12	TBA	TBA
16/02/2006	13	TBA	TBA
16/02/2006	14	TBA	TBA
16/02/2006	15	TBA	TBA

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 16.02.06

FLIGHT: B175

OPERATOR: GC/HC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Power ON 0450	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓		
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓		
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓		
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓		
	Turn on: Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓		
	Turn on Alcatel...100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓		
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓	Monitor Pump Currents	
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓		
0640 Turbo pump 6 ON...100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓			
Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓	Approx 2.8V, 0.9A		
Pre-Brief 0650	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓		
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓	Approx 125Hz	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓		
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓		
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	NEGATIVE NUMBER	
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓		
Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 16.02.06

FLIGHT: B175

OPERATOR: GC

HC

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
07:00	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	F=1.922 AB 3.1 MHz
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds in tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMS\AMSCODE\AMSMENU.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
	Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓		
	Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓		

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 16/2/06 FLIGHT: 1575

OPERATOR: G. Mc.

Tuning

NBT
accepted

TIME: 0705	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	14	16	22
Def Outer	9	10	11
Heater Bias	-6.25	-6.22	-6.5
Focus	11.50	12.25	12.5
Extraction	152	148	220

586 -13%

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME: 0713	New	Typical
KV	2.625	n/a
KV Change	-0.025	0.025kV
Gain	3.15 10^4	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.018	1

FSC 0.0109

TIME:	New	Typical
KV		n/a
KV Change		0.025kV
Gain		3.00E+06
G used Change		1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME: 0752	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.4 10^4	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	4.117	4
IPP NO3	206	400
IPP NH4	246	550
Airbeam MS	3.49	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.57	2.00E+06
Run Number	21003	n/a

1927

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)		2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)		4
IPP NO3		400
IPP NH4		550
Airbeam MS		2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF		2.00E+06
Run Number		n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	13:01:24	SMT
Run number	21554	AT 0220

21003
13:56 Au AT
21647 FL2200

TIME:	
Run number	

INLET
VALUE USED
IS THE ONE APPLIED TO THE SCANNING SYSTEM

VACC Log sheet

Set flows on ground ONLY, record when changing level

Date 16/2/05 Flight# 175 Project: DODO HC OPERATOR

Counter voltage check - Laser Volts - 8.2V.

Time (UT)	Alt. (ft)	Sample (4)	Sheath (15)	Rotam (2)	Comments
09:43	FL170	3	10	1 set to 2	Power Beakers Not all a until this time - sorry blame Williams he did set up at 9:50:45 reads 09:50:43 on VACC left as is.
09:51:40	FL060	35	13	23 reset to 2	
10:38:37	7000	35	13	2	Dart beam only but software keeps tripping out. All flows left as is. Spectra look ok and extend out but software problem.
10:45:00		3	12	16 changed to 2	tripped out again Reset
11:02:00		3	12	2	Again had to reset, again All flows checked + left.
11:19:26		3	12	2	Had to reset again after about 15 mins for pump to drop manual gases → no one said coop
11:29:58		3	12	2	Software reset / flows run 5 remain same
11:54		32	14	2.5 reset to 2	Sealed on run 6

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 175** Date: 16th February 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	N		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	Y	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B175

Date: 16 February 2006

Instruments

1. JW not operated
2. Preflight noticed stone chip on forward lower bbr
- 3.
- 4.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B175:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x forward Facing Cameras
2 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr. Eleanor J. Highwood

Senior Lecturer in Climate Physics
Department of Meteorology
University of Reading
Reading
RG6 6BB

Tel: +44 (0) 118 378 6688
Fax: +44 (0) 118 378 8905

E-mail: e.j.highwood@reading.ac.uk